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Supporting Teachers of Ukrainian Refugees

Resources for responsive teaching

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Participants:

Celia Antoniou
Fernanda Batista
Irena Brenčič
Merve Erdem
Laura Javoršek
Breda Jesenik Kolar
Renata Kecmaniuk
Reinhard Marx
Lucija Medimurec
Sílvia Maria Castanho Morgado
de Oliveira de Ramadas
Günter Renner
Anton Strnisa
Zala Vidic
Tina Vižintin
Barbara Zorn
Karin Žvan

Expert Speakers:

Ingrid M. Rodrick Beiler
Yuliana Lavrysh
Marie Rödemark
Fotini Efthymiou
Paraskevi Vassiliou
Kostas Stylianos

Facilitators:

Anna Nicolaou
Greta Björk Gudmundsdottir
Shannon Sauro
Pia Sundqvist

Compiled by:

Lucia Demarchi
Shannon Sauro

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Introduction

In Fall 2022, the VALIANT Project's virtual exchange on *Supporting Teachers of Ukrainian Refugees*, brought together teachers from across Europe who were working with or were preparing to work with Ukrainian students who had been displaced by the war. Each week, participants learned from invited expert speakers about the specific needs of Ukrainian students and how to support their learning. Topics included teaching advice from experienced teachers of Ukrainian students, strategies for vocabulary building, information about Universal design for learners and trauma-informed teaching, the social and cultural background and needs of Ukrainian learners, and multilingual approaches for working with newcomer students. Participants had the chance to collaborate and to build community with fellow colleagues across Europe for the purpose of ongoing support and resource-sharing after the conclusion of the virtual exchange.

This mini e-booklet is a compilation of questions, ideas and resources participants gathered from the four expert speaker sessions in response to three scenarios or challenges that transnational teams identified as crucial when teaching Ukrainian students. The following sections are organized according to these three guiding challenges followed by a collection of online resources shared during the virtual exchange.

Challenge 1 LANGUAGE– a barrier or a window to inclusion

Language can be the very first friend or foe when starting learning in another school/country/scenario. Is language a window or a barrier to inclusion?

Critical Questions

1. Which translation apps are useful for phone, computer (advantages, disadvantages)?
2. Are there online resources or materials that could be helpful to the teacher?
3. Where should we look to get information about languages, scripts and the school system (grading method) for each country?
4. How can teachers get learners attention and motivation when their country is in disarray due to the impact of war?
5. Is there a legal basis for foreign students to have another teacher in their class for a certain period of time? Does this depend on the country?
6. What can a teacher who has learned inappropriate pronunciation during their schooling do?
7. How can teachers make a lesson effective and keep the children motivated despite the language barrier?

Key Points & Lessons Learned

1. Children from Ukraine should not be swamped with work at school in the morning since they also attend classes in the afternoon. Many students experience hardships at school; students from war zones even more so. It is important to realize that this really affects the functioning of their brains. It is important to adjust the learning process, show understanding and understanding that progress can be slow, step by step, but progress is always progress. Let's not demand too much of ourselves if we need some time.
2. We have different opportunities and ways to learn a foreign language. Teachers have different foreign language skills, so we can feel

uncomfortable. It is important to relax, start communication, gradually our communication will improve. It is important not to remain silent.

3. It is important to involve parents in the learning process. In order to be effective, the class rules have to be set from the beginning of the course, but flexibility is also very important. When teaching, you must pay attention to students voices: their interests, needs, perceptions, experiences, ideologies.
4. Language is a passport not a barrier! It is very important for children refugees to learn a new language as soon as possible in order to maintain contact more easily.
5. It's understandable that foreign students have different backgrounds (history); changing countries, schools, education systems is stressful, but students are very flexible and learn quickly. We have to keep a positive attitude, listen to them from time to time and support them in strong areas. We can give them time to adjust, find their place again and adjust their goals.
6. Through observation and communication, we get to know the student, their prior knowledge and background, what helps them, etc. How to make the student feel that he is important, that he can express what he feels and how to gradually encourage him to explore and use a foreign language in a foreign context.

Challenge 2 What cultural aspects play a crucial role

This second challenge recognizes that cultural aspects play a crucial role while teaching Ukrainian students.

Critical Questions

1. What resources are available for supporting Ukrainian pupils?
2. What is the right dose for these students so that they are not overburdened, but at the same time they can successfully integrate and learn?
3. How can teachers align in their classrooms with the online teaching the students get from home via Zoom etc.?
4. How many years does it take someone to learn another language for everyday use?
5. When and how can teachers bring in grammar?
6. How could this be revised for different levels of learners?

Key Points & Lessons Learned

1. One very interesting observation which could really help to create a more inclusive environment during the learning process was the fact that the learners were invited to use their L1 during writing activities and then revisit their writings to work out the target language equivalents. In this way, using the L1 was encouraged rather than being viewed as something negative.
2. A very interesting tip was the use of the human figure in silhouette form to create a language portrait as a way of enabling children to talk about their feelings towards different languages. Creating a safe place was one of the most important things we will take away from this session.
3. The cultural aspect is very important to consider in education. Even more so, their current situation and the traumatic conditions in which they find themselves.

4. Including immigrants to teach immigrants can be very successful.
5. The teachers' views can help with a variety of aspects: materials and ideas about activities, etc. Adapt the content to the environment from which they come

Challenge 3 How to balance learning needs with personal needs

This scenario recognizes the challenge of balancing learning situations and learning needs with the personal challenges each Ukrainian student is facing as a result of the war.

Critical Questions

1. How much time should be given to these students to adopt to new school, to a new culture?
2. Should a teacher also learn the language of the students from Ukraine?
3. What content should be included at the introductory meeting of migrant students?

Key Points & Lessons Learned

1. Each Ukrainian student has a personal history and is faced with different challenges. We, teachers are often not equipped with the tools to deal with their issues and are left to our own resourcefulness and experience.
2. Be patient, take small steps and be supportive, give them examples how to use different apps that can help them with translation.
3. It is important to build positive relationships between all students, to allow them to show their strong points (their knowledge of a certain subject).
4. Small steps lead to success, tables with pictures of various objects ,sound recordings, the way we talk, positive thinking, connecting people in the community, creating a safe environment.
5. Listen to your students and to involve them into learning process as much as possible, encourage their strong subjects to help others so they feel more confident.

Resources

Session 1. Introduction to the Virtual Exchange

- Includeed (2022). Guide for the linguistic inclusion of immigrants. Ediciones Universidad de Salamanca.
<https://eusal.es/eusal/catalog/view/978-84-1311-655-6/6096/8003-4>

Session 2. Multilingual Approaches with Newcomer Students

- CUNY translanguaging pedagogy resources: <https://www.cuny-nysieb.org/>
- ECML plurilingual education resource page: <http://bit.ly/1Pr0Ltw>
- Further ECML resources :
<https://www.ecml.at/Resources/ECMLresources/tabid/277/language/en-GB/Default.aspx>
- Language portraits: <https://heteroglossia.net>
- Research blog: Anna Mendoza, [the #Multi/plural turn](#)
- Gail Prasad's examples of creative projects for reflecting on linguistic identity <http://www.iAMPLURILINGUAL.COM/>
- Global Storybooks projects, with multimedia online stories in a variety of languages including Ukrainian (<https://globalstorybooks.net/>)

Session 3. Universal Design for Learning as a Tool to Create a Safe and Engaging Learning Environment

- Podcast (2022), "For Ukrainian refugees, school is urgent", OECD, <https://doi.org/10.1787/c676fbc9-en>
- Koehler, C., N. Palaiologou and O. Brussino (2022), "Holistic refugee and newcomer education in Europe: Mapping, upscaling and institutionalising promising practices from Germany, Greece and the Netherlands", *OECD Education Working Papers*, No. 264, OECD Publishing, Paris, <https://dx.doi.org/10.1787/9ea58c54-en>.
- McBrien, J. (2022), "Social and emotional learning (SEL) of newcomer and refugee students: Beliefs, practices and implications for policies across OECD countries", *OECD Education Working Papers*, No. 266, OECD Publishing, Paris, <https://dx.doi.org/10.1787/a4a0f635-en>.<https://dx.doi.org/10.1787/a4a0f635-en>.
- UNHCR Teaching About Refugees 2021 - Stress and Trauma Guidebook
<https://www.unhcr.org/publications/brochures/6177f8724/unhcr-teaching-refugees-2021-stress-trauma-guidebook.html>
- Trauma-informed pedagogy
<https://library.quilford.edu/c.php?g=1063074&p=774882>
- CAST: [The UDL Guidelines](#)

- Information on Education system in Ukraine
<https://enic.in.ua/index.php/en/educationl-system/secondary-education/elementary-secondary-education>
- [Ukraine's National Curriculum](https://theewc.org/resources/school-education-in-ukraine/) <https://theewc.org/resources/school-education-in-ukraine/>
- [Learn Ukrainian For Beginners: Most Important Words And Phrases In Ukrainian || English/Ukrainian](#)
- [Timothy Snyder: The Making of Modern Ukraine.](#)
- [The Ukrainian Language: The Heroic Story of a Language That Just Won't Quit](#)
- [Ukraine: History, Culture and Identities](#)

Session 4. Five words a day: Building vocabulary knowledge with beginners

- [5 Words a Day Model](#) in Swedish for Ukrainian Students

Session 5. Teaching Ukrainian students through their “voices”: Language teachers share their experiences

- [English-Ukrainian pictograms for students and teachers](#)